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A Weakly Supervised Multimodal Deep Learning Approach for Large-Scale Tree Classification: A Case Study in Cyprus

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Abstract: Forest ecosystems play an essential role in ecological balance, supporting biodiversity and climate change mitigation. These ecosystems are crucial not only for ecological stability but also for the local economy. Performing a tree census at a country scale via traditional methods is resource-demanding, error-prone, and requires significant effort by a large number of experts. While emerging technologies such as satellite imagery and AI provide the means for achieving promising results in this task with less effort, considerable effort is still required by experts to annotate hundreds or thousands of images. This study introduces a novel methodology for a tree census classification system which leverages historical and partially labeled data, employs probabilistic data imputation and a weakly supervised training technique, and thus achieves state-of-the-art precision in classifying the dominant tree species of Cyprus. A crucial component of our methodology is a ResNet50 model which takes as input high spatial resolution satellite imagery in the visible band and near-infrared band, as well as topographical features. By applying a multimodal training approach, a classification accuracy of 90% among nine targeted tree species is achieved.

Keywords: remote sensing; deep learning; satellite imagery; tree census; forestry

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1. Introduction

Forests occupy about one third of Earth's surface [1] and have a significant impact on the balance of our biosphere. As storehouses of biological diversity, they play an important role in the life support system of Earth. They act as moderators of ecosystems, protect and replenish water and air, and are critical to the carbon balance on the planet. They provide several ecosystem services [2], like material resources, timber, and non-timber products, regulating services including climate and water quality, habitat or provisioning, supporting services, including soil formation and nutrient cycling, and cultural services relating to recreation and spirituality.

A recent study on the effects of climate change on forestry [3] revealed that the conditions in forests and their capacity to deliver environmental services are on the brink of being destabilized. Global warming causes fluctuations in rainfall, increased frequency of high-intensity storms and hurricanes, and an increase in CO₂ concentrations in the atmosphere, which affects the growth of trees [4]. Disturbances to forests due to climate change cause them to store less carbon dioxide, thereby accelerating global warming.

Due to this important role of forestry and trees, appropriate forest management and conservation efforts are essential. These efforts are only possible when policy and decision makers have accurate information about forests and their potential threats [5]. An important part of this information is accurate tree censuses and classification at high spatial resolutions. A regular forest inventory assists in the assessment of the extent of forest depletion, deforestation, synchronized restoration measures, and effectiveness of conservation programs [6]. Furthermore, functional identification of tree species and their health statuses allows for accurate estimation of the carbon stock and other ecosystem services.

Performing a tree census at scale via traditional methods is resource-demanding, as it requires significant effort by a large number of experts. At the same time, traditional methods are error-prone because humans are heavily involved in the process. Such methods demand high costs and significant time, are rather static, and do not allow the detection of rapid disturbances and threats to trees and forests.

Recent technological advancements have allowed researchers to accelerate and scale up the tree census process by employing satellite imagery and artificial intelligence (AI) [7]. Satellite imagery has become increasingly accessible, offering improved spatial and temporal resolutions which enable detailed observations of forested areas. Freely available data from satellite missions like Landsat and Copernicus provide open access to moderate-resolution imagery. However, the lack of free access to high-resolution imagery from commercial providers like Maxar (e.g., WorldView) and Planet Labs (e.g., PlanetScope) can pose limitations [8]. Deep learning (DL) methods, including techniques such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and long short-term memory (LSTM) networks, have been widely applied in tree classification from satellite imagery, demonstrating their effectiveness in leveraging spectral and spatial patterns for detailed species identification [9]. However, a drawback of these models is that they require a supervised training process, which usually requires experts to annotate a large number of images to allow AI models to learn how to identify different tree species [10]. This creates significant overheads in the process, while identifying the right experts is usually difficult.

In this paper, we propose a hybrid approach where experts label data only partially, and then weakly supervised learning techniques are employed to train AI models, taking satellite imagery as input. We argue that by harnessing historical and partially labeled data, even when a portion of these data is inconsistent, we can employ data imputation techniques such as pseudo-labeling to expand the training datasets to the extent required by AI models to tackle the tree classification task with state-of-the-art precision.

We further exploit the fact that large-scale geospatial tools and digital twins are becoming available [11,12], providing detailed and highly accurate geomorphological and topographical characteristics of Earth. Combining high spatial resolution visible-band and near-infrared (NIR)-band satellite imagery together with geoanalytical services provided by those tools, AI models can be trained on multiple modalities [13,14], allowing solving the tree census problem with high accuracy, minimal effort, and lower costs. Thus, the main contribution of this paper is the introduction of a novel methodology for a tree census classification system which leverages historical and partially labeled data, employing data imputation and weakly supervised learning techniques and thus achieving the classification of the dominant tree species of Cyprus with state-of-the-art precision.

This study aims to build a cost-effective and scalable methodology which can be used to classify tree species over a wide geographical area. Instead of being solely reliant on large and accurate datasets which are difficult to acquire, our approach leverages a weak supervision technique in the form of pseudo-labeling along with auxiliary geomorphological data, which are used together for multi-modal deep learning. This methodology reduces the dependency on large, fully annotated datasets, allowing it to be applied for large-scale coverage of geographical areas. At the same time, this study provides new evidence that the general idea of employing larger and rather incomplete datasets to train deep learning models for the tree mapping task from satellite imagery works well in comparison with using smaller and more precise datasets. This evidence aligns with the work of Rolnick et al. [15], who showed that deep neural networks are capable of generalizing from training data, for which true labels are massively outnumbered by incorrect labels. They specifically diluted each clean training example with 100 randomly labeled examples and still achieved quite good results on several datasets. Training in the regime of substantial label noise requires a significant but manageable increase in dataset size that is related to the factor by which correct labels have been diluted. Similarly, in our approach, each existing tree label is diffused at neighboring areas and characterizes unknown nearby trees. Since the probability of two trees of the same species growing close to each other is (at least slightly)

higher than the probability of two different trees growing in neighboring locations, our pseudo-label assignment process will never harm the training process, but on the contrary, it will most likely improve the results if it is applied systematically and consistently. Given that the errors introduced by the pseudo-labeling process are generated uniformly in the sense that the process is applied to large areas of evenly distributed tree species (in terms of the area covered by each species), the proposed weakly supervised approach can only improve the results and is more cost-effective than using a smaller but more precisely annotated dataset via a costly and time-consuming process.

2. Related Work

Ground assessment of tree resources is time-consuming, especially in dense forested areas. The recent progress in remote sensing and DL has improved the quality of tree species classification and mapping initiatives. Remote sensing provides large-scale coverage and more frequent surveying, making it a promising alternative method for classifying tree species rather effectively. In this section, we describe prominent work in this field, while Table 1 summarizes the main results of the related efforts under study.

Regarding medium spatial resolution satellite imagery, Axelsson et al. [16] demonstrated that Sentinel-2 can be effectively used in tree species classification. Similarly, Persson et al. [17] and Puletti et al. [18] showcased the use of Sentinel-2 for the classification of forest types and tree species with similar assertions.

Moreover, high spatial resolution satellite imagery (e.g., from IKONOS or WorldView satellites) has been employed, harnessing better-quality images of tree canopies. For instance, Immitzer et al. [19] studied the classification of three tree species of a temperate forest in Germany using WorldView-2. Likewise, Fang et al. [20] used multi-temporal WorldView-3 imagery to classify tree species at different taxonomic levels in Washington, D.C. Generally, the shift from medium to high spatial resolution imagery results in improved classification precision due to the enhanced detail captured in the imagery.

Combining visible-band satellite imagery with other modalities such as airborne LiDAR and multispectral imagery can aid in the tree classification challenge. For example, Wang et al. [21] showed that the integration of LiDAR with visible-band satellite imagery led to a 10% increase in classification accuracy. Immitzer et al. [22] found out that the approach of using additional spectral bands from multispectral imagery significantly improved the user's accuracy by 8% in classifying various tree species.

Modern approaches incorporate AI-based techniques such as random forests [23], CNNs, LSTMs, and multilayer perceptrons (MLPs), which offer great capabilities in identifying and classifying tree species [9]. For instance, Welle et al. [24] used Sentinel-2 imagery and the XGBoost ML model to map tree species across Germany, harnessing multi-temporal and multi-spectral data to capture species phenology across seasons. Likewise, Lechner et al. [14] fused data from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 for enhancing species categorization in the Wienerwald Biosphere Reserve in Austria. Furthermore, a study by He et al. [7] in Qingyuan County, China demonstrated that the ResNet50 [25] model performed best in comparison with several implemented DL models. Also, the authors demonstrated the complexity of differentiating relatively similar species by utilizing the application of alternative image analysis methods (such as PCA), and additional data inputs (e.g., the NDVI index) may improve the species classification process. Similarly, Li et al. [26] examined several CNN structures (i.e., ResNet [27] and DenseNet [28]) for the classification of individual tree species using high spatial resolution satellite imagery, further demonstrating the applicability of CNNs in improving the tree classification task. These studies demonstrate the increasing precision and scalability of DL techniques across different landscapes.

Other studies have shown that the inclusion of geomorphological data such as digital elevation models (DEMs) and topographical features enhances classification accuracy, especially in hilly or mountainous areas. Prodromou et al. [13] used random forests to map the main forest habitats of Cyprus using Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 satellite imagery along with topographical features and achieved a significant improvement in overall accuracy of

10% in comparison with using Sentinel-2 alone. Liu et al. [29] noted that the integration of DEMs with Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, and Landsat-8 imagery improved the overall accuracy for forest species in Wuhan city, China by 5.96%. In the same manner, Chiang et al. [30] identified the major tree species in northern Mongolia by employing Landsat 8 imagery along with the topographic factors obtained from ASTER GDEM v2. Their results showed that incorporating variables such as elevation, slope, aspect, and the topographic wetness index significantly increased the overall accuracy from 71% to 81%. The significance of integrating geomorphological features in tree classification was also showcased by Yu et al. [31] in a study of Inner Mongolia's grasslands and by Chiang et al. [32] in a study of Mongolia's mountainous regions.

Finally, weakly supervised learning-based approaches look promising for overcoming data limitations in tree species classification. A recent attempt by Illarionova et al. [33] employed weakly supervised learning for tree classification in Russian boreal forests based on Sentinel-2 imagery. Their methodology addressed issues of weak and uneven ground truth information by using a weakly supervised neural network architecture which corrected the species markup in line with the sorts of species peculiar to stands. Adding this weak markup to the object-wise sampling techniques enhanced the overall classification performance (F1 score from 0.68 to 0.76).

To sum up, Table 1 lists the key findings of each paper mentioned above, indicating the study area, datasets used, the type of classification task under study, the techniques employed, the number of classes involved, and the results based on the different metric(s) employed by each author. We can conclude that higher spatial resolution satellite data allow for better results, with improvements of 5–10% in the overall accuracy [26]. DL models have better performance in classification tasks involving multiple classes, achieving 84.91% classification accuracy in [7]. Also, the integration of topographic information improves classification results, with an overall accuracy increase of 10% in [13], because topographic features influence vegetation types and distributions.

Table 1. Overview of techniques and outcomes in forest classification and monitoring.

Authors	Study Area	Data Used	Task	Technique or Model Used	Classes	Results
Immitzer et al. [19]	Bavaria, Germany	WorldView-2 and Landsat	Tree species classification and mapping	Random forest	3	$R^2 = 0.76$
Li et al. [26]	York University, Toronto, Canada	WorldView-2	Individual tree species classification	ResNet18	4	Overall accuracy: 90.9%
Fang et al. [20]	Washington, DC, USA	WorldView-3	Tree species classification	Random forest	19	Overall accuracy: 61.3%
Yin et al. [34]	Central Asia	WorldView-3	Forest cover mapping	Random forest	3	Overall accuracy: 83%
Axelsson et al. [16]	Southern Sweden	Sentinel-2	Tree species classification	Bayesian inference with maximum likelihood classification	4	Overall accuracy: 87%
Persson et al. [17]	Remningstorp, Sweden	Sentinel-2	Tree species classification	Random forest	5	Overall accuracy: 88.2%
Puletti et al. [18]	Tuscany, Italy	Sentinel-2	Tree species classification	Random forest	4	Overall accuracy: 86.2%

Table 1. Cont.

Authors	Study Area	Data Used	Task	Technique or Model Used	Classes	Results
Welle et al. [24]	German forests	Sentinel-2	Dominant tree species classification	XGBoost	7	F1 scores from 0.69 to 0.96
Lechner et al. [14]	Wienerwald Biosphere Reserve, Austria	Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2	Tree species classification	Random forest	12	Overall accuracy: 83.7%
He et al. [7]	Qingyuan County, Zhejiang Province, China	Sentinel-2	Forest tree species classification	ResNet50	8	Validation accuracy: 84.91%
Prodromou et al. [13]	Cyprus (Paphos, Akamas, Troodos)	Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, and topographical features	Forest habitat mapping in Natura2000 sites	Random forest (RF)	8 in Akamas, 9 in Paphos, 6 in Troodos	Overall accuracy: 91–94%
Liu et al. [29]	Wuhan, China	Sentinel-1A, Sentinel-2A, Landsat-8, DEM	Forest type classification	Object-based random forest	9	Overall accuracy: 82.78%
Chiang et al. [30]	Erdenebulgan County, Mongolia	Landsat 8 and ASTER GDEM	Tree species classification	Maximum entropy (MaxEnt)	4	Overall accuracy: 81%
Yu et al.'s [31]	Inner Mongolia, China	Sentinel-2 and DEM	Grassland classification	Random forest	3	Overall accuracy: 83.41–96.97%
Illarionova et al. [33]	Leningrad Oblast, Russia	Sentinel-2	Tree species classification	CNN with weakly supervised classification and object-wise sampling	4	F1 score: 0.76

3. Study Area and Tree Classes

The study focuses on the geographical area of the Republic of Cyprus, an island in the Eastern Mediterranean renowned for its rich biodiversity and unique flora. Cyprus boasts a variety of tree types, each with distinct ecological characteristics and significance.

For this study, nine specific classes of trees were selected, representing the major tree types found across the island [13]. These classes are as follows:

- ***Cedrus brevifolia* (Cyprus cedar):** Found only in the Troodos Mountain range, the Cyprus cedar plays a huge role in the country's flora. A recent study [35] substantiated its high gene flow and distinctive populational distribution. In this regard, the necessity of this species reservation is crucial.
- ***Ceratonio rhamnion* (carob and rhamnus shrubs):** These trees [36], which mostly thrive at lower elevations, are characterized by the carob tree (*Ceratonia siliqua*) as well as different types of Rhamnus shrubs. They are vital in soil stabilization and local agriculture, and research stresses their significant function in supporting local biological diversity.
- ***Juniperus* (Juniper):** Juniper forests [37] contain species such as *Juniperus oxycedrus* and *Juniperus phoenicea*, which are widespread on the island, especially in rocky, mountainous terrains. These forests are important to the Mediterranean climate of the

island because they are significant in discouraging the occurrence of soil erosion and supporting local wildlife.

- **Fruit bearing (broadleaf and fruit-bearing trees):** Some of the species found in this group include strawberry, fig (*Ficus carica*), and lemon (*Citrus limon*) [38]. These trees are essential to the ecology of Cyprus since they offer shelter to many animals and also play the role of acting as a nutrient pump which sustains many living organisms and checks and balances the availability of nutrients in the ecosystem.
- **Olive (olive trees):** One can distinguish Olive groves as a widespread and culturally valuable kind of Cypriot vegetation [39] which has economic significance and is also known to be climate change-resistant. They have been extensively evaluated for their contribution to agroforestry.
- ***Pinus brutia* (Turkish pine):** Turkish pine trees found in the coastal and lowland areas [40] are extremely resistant and remarkably significant to supporting the various forms of wildlife on the island. They are important to a host of wildlife species, and as recent investigations have shown, these systems have developed various coping mechanisms and are critical to fire functions.
- ***Pinus nigra* (black pine):** Black pine trees are mostly rooted at a higher altitude in the Troodos Mountains [41]. These trees are extremely important for their impact on biodiversity and the water catchment areas. Especially of high value for timber, research studies on the genetics and conservation status of *Pinus nigra* have emerged most recently.
- ***Quercus alnifolia* (golden oak):** This oak species [42] is solely found in the Troodos Mountains and is characterized by its golden leaves. This species is important for maintaining the balance of local ecosystems as it hosts endemic animals.
- **Vine (vineyards):** Wine production and the growing of wine-making Vines [43], most famously located in the Paphos and Limassol regions, are important facets of Cyprus's agricultural industry as well as its history. The viticulture—that is, the growing of grapevines—has been a focus of recent research, especially the effects of climate change on yields and sustainability in vineyards.

4. Methodology

This study involved three main steps: (1) data acquisition; (2) data preprocessing and pseudo-labeling; and (3) DL model development, training, and validation. Due to the limited availability of labeled data for individual trees, this study adopted a weakly supervised learning approach. By leveraging pseudo-labeling, the method augmented the dataset, addressing the challenge of insufficient labels while ensuring ecological consistency in the expanded dataset. Figure 1 illustrates the proposed methodology. In the following subsections, we first describe the study area, and then we explain these three steps.

Figure 1. The proposed methodology takes advantage of multimodal information at an early processing stage by integrating RGB, NIR, and topographical features. This data fusion feeds into a DL model, resulting in a final classification.

4.1. Data Acquisition

For this experiment, we considered using the visible, near-infrared satellite imagery band and topographical and geomorphological features. First, visible-band imagery data in the form of true-color composite RGB images were downloaded from Google Earth Images [44] for May 2023 at a spatial resolution of 0.2–0.5 m per pixel. The satellite image taken in May 2023 is appropriate for tree classification considering that it was taken when there was maximum vegetation cover, and thus the chlorophyll concentration was high. During this time period, NIR band reflections were higher, and the RGB images tended to be free of atmosphere inference and weather obstructions (i.e., clouds and rain). To obtain full spatial coverage, all data were downloaded based on a geospatial grid layer consisting of 4890 cells (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. The grid layer corresponding to the satellite images used in the data overlaid on a map of Cyprus.

The NIR band imagery from PlanetScope was also used for May 2023. PlanetScope, operated by Planet Labs [45], is a satellite constellation which provides high-resolution Earth imagery using small, low-cost satellites. These satellites capture multispectral images with a spatial resolution of 3–5 m per pixel covering the red, green, blue (RGB), and NIR bands. NIR band imagery is useful in the assessment of vegetation health and other features which are difficult to obtain from true-color images. Further, topographical and geomorphological features were downloaded from GAEA [12], which is an online geospatial tool offering geoanalytics for the island of Cyprus using 27 environmental services. From these services, we used elevation, slope, aspect, and soil type as the most relevant factors for tree classification.

4.2. Dataset Preprocessing and Pseudo-Labeling

In this step, activities involved the cleaning of satellite imagery and topographical features. Initially, the high-resolution RGB satellite image patches with a size of 8192×6606 pixels each were georeferenced and segmented into smaller georeferenced patches of 256×256 pixels, which corresponded to a 60×60 area. This segmentation was important for enabling localized analysis of the forested areas. Patches obscured by clouds were identified and removed. Additionally, patches near residential areas were excluded, as these regions often contain mixed land uses which could introduce noise into the analysis. Large areas of exposed ground were also removed, as shown in Figure 3. Finally, all spectral bands were normalized to have a mean value of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. Furthermore, to achieve a unified resolution for the inputs of our model, we used bilinear interpolation to resize the low-resolution bands to match the visible-band resolution.

Figure 3. Examples of images manually removed from the dataset to facilitate the training of the model by reducing data ambiguity: (a) cloud-covered fields, (b) residential areas, and (c) empty fields.

4.2.1. Ground Truth Data

For the labeling process, as the ground truth, we utilized historical georeferenced classification data from the Department of Forestry (see Figure 4), which were collected in October 2021, and from the Ministry of Agriculture (see Figure 5) of the Republic of Cyprus, which were collected in March 2022.

For both layers, data were filtered for nine selected classes (see Section 3), which included olive, vine, and fruit-bearing trees from the agricultural layer and *Juniperus*, *Quercus alnifolia*, *Pinus nigra*, *Pinus brutia*, *Cedrus brevifolia*, and *Ceratonio rhammonion* from the forest layer. We selected these classes based on the criteria of (1) having at least 50–100 labels for each class and (2) having some cues which allow them to be classified from satellite images. As various agricultural classes had quite similar depictions (e.g., apple trees, peach trees, and citrus trees), we placed them together under the “fruit-bearing” class. At the same time, we completely removed classes with extremely few labels (less than 50), such as banana trees and palm trees. Our original data distribution can be seen in Figure 6. The agriculture-related labels were much higher compared with the forestry-related labels.

Figure 4. Ground truth annotations of forest areas provided by the Cyprus Department of Forestry.

Figure 5. Ground truth annotations of agricultural fields provided by the Cyprus Ministry of Agriculture.

Figure 6. Distribution of landscape types in the original dataset (before data imputation).

4.2.2. Data Imputation via Pseudo-Labeling

To overcome the problem of underrepresented classes and partial data, we utilized a data imputation technique to augment the data for the forest-related classes by applying the nearest neighbor method to assign labels to each point based on the closest known (i.e., annotated by experts) data points within a 200 m radius. To achieve this, we utilized the Quantum Geographic Information System (QGIS), which is open-source software used for geospatial tasks. The *distance to nearest hub (points)* function was applied on the filtered vector layer of forest classes. After performing the interpolation, we visualized the interpolated points and removed the overlapping points, as shown in Figures 7 and 8. This approach reduced the class imbalance in the dataset at the cost of obtaining the wrong labels. This risk proved to be substantially lower than the problem posed by the complete lack of labels on certain occasions. The augmented dataset distribution can be observed in Figure 9, and the number of points for each class is listed in Table 2.

Figure 7. Overlapping points.

Figure 8. Overlapping points removed.

Figure 9. Distribution of landscape types in the processed dataset (after data imputation).

Table 2. Number of labeled points per class before and after performing pseudo-labeling.

Class	Original Georeferenced Points	Pseudo-Labeled Georeferenced Points
<i>Cedrus brevifolia</i>	54	1769
Ceratonio rhamnonion	203	8114
<i>Juniperus</i>	225	9454
Fruit-bearing	12,613	12,613
Olive	36,084	36,084
<i>Pinus brutia</i> (Turkish pine)	502	21,194
<i>Pinus nigra</i> (Black pine)	97	4878
<i>Quercus alnifolia</i>	287	9447
Vine	18,556	18,556

After augmenting the forest dataset, we combined it with the filtered agricultural data to generate one dataset for all nine classes. Using this georeferenced layer, the RGB georeferenced patches were each labeled, with the class being closer to each 256×256 patch. From these labeled patches, we created label masks for the areas of interest. These masks were also utilized to create georeferenced patches for the NIR and topographical datasets employing aspect, slope, elevation, and soil data from the GAEA tool.

4.3. DL Model Development

DL models such as ResNet [27] and DenseNet [28] have been proven to be particularly promising in solving complex computer vision problems due to their ability to extract complex features through deep residual learning. The use of skip connections not only enhances accuracy in tree species classification [26] but also stabilizes training by reducing the risk of vanishing gradients during training [46,47]. We chose the ResNet50 model for its moderate size and because it is robust and efficient in handling high-dimensional data from Google Earth Images and PlanetScope satellite imagery. A weakly supervised learning approach was adopted, leveraging a focal loss function to optimize training while considering the use of a sparsely labeled dataset. The focal loss function used in our implementation is shown below:

$$FL(p_t) = (1 - p_t)^\gamma \times CE_Loss(p_t)$$

where the following definitions apply:

- p_t is the probability assigned to the true class.
- γ is the focusing parameter, which controls how much more the loss focuses on hard examples.
- CE_Loss refers to the cross-entropy loss between the predicted probability distribution and the ground truth labels.

Implementation was conducted on the PyTorch 1.12.1 framework on a high-performing GPU-equipped desktop workstation with the following specifications: an AMD Ryzen 9 5900X 12-Core CPU, 32 GB of RAM at 2666 MHz, an NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU with 24 GB of VRAM, a 938 GB NVMe SSD, and a 3.6 TB HDD.

Alternative architectures were considered, but ResNet50 offered a favorable trade-off in terms of accuracy and processing time, given the dataset characteristics and available computational resources. Table 3 shows the accuracy of the various models we experimented with and their corresponding training and test times.

Table 3. Comparison of models' accuracy and their training and test times.

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Train Time (per Epoch)	Test Time
MobileNet	85%	0.85	0.84	0.85	14 m 2 s	2 m 25 s
EfficientNet	87%	0.88	0.97	0.87	15 m 25 s	2 m 33 s
ResNet18	88%	0.89	0.88	0.88	17 m 40 s	2 m 51 s
ResNet50	90%	0.88	0.87	0.88	19 m 55 s	3 m 2 s

Training and Validation

The dataset was divided into 70% for training, 15% for validation, and 15% for testing. Table 4 shows the total number of images per class and their respective counts across training, validation, and testing. To further mitigate class imbalances, we adopted a data augmentation technique known as targeted augmentation [48]. For underrepresented classes, all available augmentation options were used, including resizing, flipping randomly, rotating, applying color jitter, and random erasing. The above techniques were used to improve the heterogeneity of the data in order to help the DL model generalize better. Also, weighted random sampling was utilized to address class imbalances. This sampling technique assigns higher weights to underrepresented classes to ensure balanced sampling across the classes in each batch. To avoid overtraining and unintentional overshadowing of well-represented classes, minimal augmentation [49] was applied to classes with adequate representation.

Table 4. Total number of images for each class with training, validation, and testing splits.

Class	Total Images	Training	Validation	Testing
<i>Cedrus brevifolia</i>	1953	1407	293	293
<i>Ceratonio rhamnion</i>	6989	4921	1034	1034
<i>Juniperus</i>	9388	6624	1382	1382
Fruit-bearing	11,930	8194	1868	1868
Olive	34,670	24,544	5063	5063
<i>Pinus brutia</i> (Turkish pine)	34,806	24,664	5081	5061
<i>Pinus nigra</i> (black pine)	10,092	7183	1454	1455
<i>Quercus alnifolia</i>	13,567	9605	1981	1981
Vine	22,723	15,874	3425	3424

After applying the techniques mentioned above, we redesigned the ResNet50 model architecture to incorporate the inputs of multiple modalities (i.e., RGB satellite imagery, NIR-band imagery, aspect, slope, elevation, and soil type). The focal loss function was employed to emphasize the learning of difficult-to-classify training examples. For training the model, we used the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of $1e^{-5}$. A learning rate scheduler (ReduceLROnPlateau) was also used to adjust the learning rate based on validation loss, reducing the rate by a factor of 0.5 and aiding in effective convergence. The training process incorporated early stopping to prevent overfitting, with the best model being saved based on validation performance. We halted training when the model validation loss stopped improving after 10 consecutive epochs.

Model validation involved a separate test set to ensure unbiased evaluation using the following metrics: accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score.

5. Results

This section evaluates the model's performance in terms of its precision when performing the classification task under study. Table 5 presents a comprehensive performance comparison of different ResNet50 models trained with various combinations of the multi-modal data used as input. We assumed that topographical features such as elevation, aspect, slope, and soil, integrated as auxiliary input data, would provide additional contextual information about the probability of certain tree species being found in different geomorphological landscapes of the island [50]. Starting from a ResNet50 model as a baseline, the lowest performance was observed when the model was trained on RGB images without using pretrained weights (classification accuracy of 76%). When a pretrained ResNet50 model on ImageNet data was used, the accuracy then reached 85%. By incorporating soil data, a slight improvement in the model's accuracy was observed (86%). Similarly, by adding NIR-band images together with RGB ones, the model accuracy further improved slightly (87%). Incorporating the elevation, slope, and aspect increased the accuracy to 88%. The highest performance was achieved when the AI model combined RGB and NIR images and all geomorphological characteristics (i.e., elevation, aspect, slope, and soil), reaching a classification accuracy of 90% and a score of 0.90 for all other performance metrics (F1 score, precision, and recall). These results highlight the importance of the fusion of multiple datasets and modalities for achieving high classification performance.

Table 5. Performance comparison of ResNet50 model with different combinations of input modalities.

Model	Data Sources	Accuracy	F1 Score	Precision	Recall
ResNet50	RGB (No Pretraining)	76%	0.77	0.80	0.76
	RGB	85%	0.86	0.85	0.86
	RGB + Soil	86%	0.86	0.87	0.86
	RGB + NIR	87%	0.87	0.88	0.87
	RGB + Aspect	88%	0.88	0.87	0.88
	RGB + Slope	88%	0.88	0.88	0.88
	RGB + Elevation	88%	0.88	0.89	0.88
	RGB + Elevation + NIR	89%	0.89	0.90	0.89
	RGB + Elevation + NIR + Aspect + Slope + Soil	90%	0.90	0.90	0.90

Table 6 shows the classification performance of the best-performing ResNet50 model (final row in Table 5) across all different classes. The model achieved high precision, recall, and F1 score results across most of the classes. The model exhibited the highest scores for olive trees, with a precision of 0.95, recall of 0.93, and F1 score of 0.94. Similarly, *Juniperus* and vine were accurately classified, with F1 scores of 0.91. At the same time, the *Quercus alnifolia* and *Pinus nigra* classes had slightly worse performance, with F1 scores of 0.84 and 0.87, respectively. Overall, the ResNet50 model demonstrated good performance (more than 0.80 for all metrics) for all tree classes.

The confusion matrix in Figure 10 provides a detailed breakdown of the AI model's performance across different vegetation classes, showing the number of correct and incorrect predictions for each class. Each cell in the matrix represents the count of predictions performed by the model based on the testing dataset. The diagonal cells (from the top left to the bottom right) show the number of correct predictions for each class, while the off-diagonal cells indicate misclassifications. Olive trees had the highest accuracy with 4776 correct predictions, while *Cedrus brevifolia* was correctly predicted 274 times with minimal misclassification errors. Misclassifications occurred mainly between similar classes (i.e., classes with low variance), such as *Pinus brutia* and *Pinus nigra*, as well as between fruit-bearing trees and olive trees. These misclassifications were likely due to shared spectral or textural features as well as potential overlaps in their ecological environments, which the

model found challenging to separate. Overall, the model demonstrated strong classification abilities with most predictions correctly identified, as indicated by the concentration along the diagonal. Despite these strengths, further refinement of the input features, inclusion of additional training data for overlapping classes, or incorporation of advanced feature engineering techniques could help mitigate the observed confusion between closely related classes. This will be explored as part of future work.

Table 6. Classification performance metrics of the proposed approach for the dominant tree species in Cyprus.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
<i>Cedrus brevifolia</i>	0.85	0.94	0.89
Ceratonio rhamnion	0.88	0.91	0.90
<i>Juniperus</i>	0.93	0.90	0.91
Fruit-bearing	0.88	0.87	0.88
Olives	0.95	0.93	0.94
<i>Pinus brutia</i> (Turkish pine)	0.90	0.86	0.88
<i>Pinus nigra</i> (Black pine)	0.84	0.91	0.87
<i>Quercus alnifolia</i>	0.81	0.87	0.84
Vine	0.89	0.93	0.91

Figure 10. The confusion matrix compares the predicted and actual classes, highlighting classification accuracy and misclassification patterns.

Geographical Distance for Pseudo-Labeling

Here, we show how our experimentation performed in order to consider the best performing distance for the pseudo-labeling approach of our ground truth data (see Section 4.2.2). We performed experiments for pseudo-labeling based on geographical distances from the ground truth labels of 50, 100, 200, 300, and 400 m. We trained the ResNet50 model using the best configuration of data sources, which was the combination of RGB and NIR images, elevation, slope, aspect, and soil (see Table 5). The results are shown in Table 7. The results suggest that a distance of 200 m was the best choice for the pseudo-labeling process.

Table 7. Classification results for different pseudo-labeling distances. For all cases, we used the ResNet-50 model and all available modalities (RGB images, elevation, NIR images, slope, soil, and aspect).

Distance	Accuracy	F1 Score	Precision	Recall
50 (m)	88%	0.85	0.83	0.87
100 (m)	88%	0.85	0.84	0.86
200 (m)	90%	0.90	0.90	0.90
300 (m)	88%	0.87	0.86	0.88
400 (m)	87%	0.86	0.85	0.87

6. Discussion

The adoption of satellite imagery and AI, together with the inclusion of topographical features for tree classification, apart from improving the census of forestry resources, also plays a crucial role in forest carbon inventory and stock assessment. This approach has been proven to be highly beneficial, particularly in remote areas which are difficult to reach on foot. It offers not only a cost-effective alternative to ground surveys but also constitutes a dynamic methodology for frequent surveying, which is crucial for prompt decision making and policy development. The findings of our study underscore the effectiveness of integrating high spatial resolution visible-band satellite imagery, NIR imagery, and topographical features as multi-modal inputs of DL models for achieving a high classification accuracy of tree species. Most importantly, the results of our study indicate that country-scale surveys can be achieved only by means of sparsely labeled data and weakly supervised approaches for training AI models, where specific techniques such as pseudo-labeling seem to work well. This study also shows that using an extensive but partially incomplete dataset to train a deep learning model can be more effective for tree mapping from satellite imagery compared with relying solely on smaller and highly accurate datasets.

6.1. AI Model Performance

The ResNet50 model trained on RGB and NIR images and the elevation, slope, aspect, and soil performed best, with a classification accuracy of 90% on the testing data for nine tree species classes. Table 5 shows the impact of integrating multiple sources of relevant data for training DL models, where each additional source contributed, to a certain extent, to improving the classification results. It is likely that multi-temporal and multi-spectral (aside from NIR) satellite data as well as LIDAR data could further improve accuracy. This is a task for future work.

In comparison with existing state-of-the-art research on tree species classification based on satellite imagery and AI [16,17,24], our results show state-of-the-art performance, while their significance is more profound due to the weakly supervised approach which followed. It is difficult to directly compare our results with other works because of the different techniques, datasets, metrics, numbers of classes, and input data used. We claim with some caution that our AI model surpasses the findings of He et al. [7], where an 84.91% validation accuracy was achieved on the FTSD dataset. He et al. achieved this score by utilizing PCA and NDVI based on Sentinel-2 satellite imagery for classifying nine tree species. Similarly, Lechner et al. [14] utilized Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data for tree classification, reaching a classification accuracy of 83.2%. By adding additional data from Landsat-8 and topographic features, together with Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 imagery, Liu et al. [29] achieved an accuracy of 82.78%.

A possible reason for the good performance of our ResNet50 model is its capacity to capture and properly encode a wide number of diverse input modalities. The confusion matrix in Table 6 shows that the accuracy was high for the majority of the tree classes. Our approach achieved precision and recall values close to 0.9 for the olive, *Juniperus*, and vine

classes. Most misclassifications occurred between *Pinus brutia* and *Pinus nigra* as well as between fruit-bearing and olive trees. This happened due to the similar characteristics of those classes, which made it easy to confuse one with the other. Also, this confusion can be attributed to their similar spectral signatures in satellite imagery, which are challenging to distinguish. Some lower accuracy in some classes, such as in *Quercus alnifolia* and *Pinus nigra*, can be explained by the small number of training examples available.

6.2. Topographical Features and Tree Species

When examining the relation between the topographical features and tree classes, we developed a range of geovisualizations. In Figure 11, the distribution of tree classes is shown in relation to the elevation using a box plot. Tree classes have different elevation preferences. For example, *Quercus alnifolia* is found at higher elevations with an interquartile range (IQR) of 600–1000 m. *Cedrus brevifolia* and *Pinus nigra* prefer hilly areas and flourish in the mid-near range of 1000 m. However, the height range for vine, olive, and Juniper trees is wide, being more common at elevations below 500 m. *Pinus brutia* and *Cedrus brevifolia* seem to adapt to different elevations, whereas Ceratonio rhamnion has a narrower distribution.

Figure 11. Distribution of tree classes with elevation.

Similarly, when examining the relation between soil type and tree class, Figure 12 indicates that olive trees tend to grow in diverse soils, especially loam, clay, and rocky types, while Ceratonio rhamnion appears mostly in rocky and loamy soils. Fruit-bearing trees grow in gravelly sand and loamy soil, while *Quercus alnifolia* prefers rocky and loam soils.

Figure 12. Occurrence of tree classes with soil type.

6.3. Interpretation of Results

The Department of Forestry of the Republic of Cyprus is concerned about the spatial expansion of the *Pinus nigra* tree species, which creates competition with the more native *Pinus brutia* species. Our tree census allows understanding the trends regarding this expansion, as well as which geomorphological conditions favor this expansion. Figure 13 illustrates that *Pinus nigra* prefers higher elevations compared with *Pinus brutia*. While both tree species tend to grow in rocky mountain areas, *Pinus brutia* grows in sandy areas as well, as can be seen in Figure 14. Such observations are significant for local policymakers, while the velocity of the expansion of *Pinus brutia* is also important for them to assess the urgency of the problem and the need to take direct measures or not.

Figure 13. Distribution of *Pinus nigra* and *Pinus brutia* with elevation.

Figure 14. Occurrence of *Pinus nigra* and *Pinus brutia* with soil type.

6.4. Limitations

While this study marks an advancement in tree classification and forest censuses based on earth observation and AI, mainly because of the methodology followed to achieve this (i.e., weakly supervised learning), there are certain limitations worth mentioning. First, the study included only nine tree classes, due to the fact that only those classes had at least 50 images annotated, even with the data imputation methods used. Classes such as palm trees, banana trees, walnut trees, and fig trees were left out. Furthermore, a limitation of our study is the fact that our testing was based on the ground truth information originally provided by experts (Department of Forestry) and not any visual inspection of the results performed afterward by the same or other experts.

6.5. Future Work

Future research will focus on including additional tree species classes and employing experts to further validate our classification results. We also plan to perform tree classification for previous years (e.g., 10 years ago) to assess the velocity of the spatial expansion of *Pinus nigra*, as requested by local policy makers. Moreover, we intend to experiment with multi-temporal and multi-spectral satellite imagery and investigate the potential improvements in accuracy which may be achieved. Specifically, we aim to improve the misclassifications among *Pinus brutia* and *Pinus nigra* by incorporating additional spectral bands or higher-resolution imagery, potentially refining the model's ability to capture subtle interspecies differences.

Finally, an existing problem of the related work is that the methodologies or implementations of most studies were site-specific and therefore of limited utility, being difficult to replicate in different ecosystems and landscapes. We will work on developing more robust and adaptive methodologies and models which may work effectively in diverse areas and scenarios.

7. Conclusions

This study proposes a novel methodology for a tree census classification system which leverages historical and partially labeled data, employing probabilistic data imputation and weakly supervised learning techniques to achieve classification of the dominant tree species of the whole country of Cyprus with state-of-the-art precision. A DL model was developed, taking as input high spatial resolution visible-band and near-infrared band satellite imagery as well as topographical features. By means of this multi-modal training approach, a classification accuracy of 90% among nine targeted tree species was achieved. An ablation study indicated the usefulness of incorporating topographical information for improving the classifier's performance.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

DL	Deep learning
GEE	Google Earth Engine
NIR	Near infrared
RGB	Red, green, and blue
PCA	Principal component analysis
NDVI	Normalized difference vegetation index
IQR	Interquartile range
DEMs	Digital elevation models

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